

A predictive role of the old cortex in general intelligence

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Abstract

Cross-disciplinary research has revealed many parallels between neocortical sensory information processing and that found in artificial neural networks. Here, we argue that neural and computational insights into the hippocampus, a structurally unique and phylogenetically old cortical region, have yet to be fully leveraged by such models. The hippocampus contains a well-described neural circuitry and is situated at the nexus of multiple brain networks, allowing it to maintain latent sensory, affective, and higher order transmodal information. Recent AI developments based on self-supervised architectures that engage prediction in latent spaces are data-efficient and obey real world constraints, making them promising not only as AI models but also as neuroscientific models. We argue that within that framework, the hippocampus helps compute and maintain predictions over multiple time spans thereby increasing the number of comparisons between predicted and real latent sensory data. This may help explain why animals with a hippocampus are able to learn so efficiently compared to popular, data-hungry AI architectures. Our perspective offers new avenues towards understanding neural intelligence and the design of data-efficient, naturalistic AI.

Keywords: Neuroscience, Artificial Intelligence, Predictive Coding, Hippocampus, AGI

Highlights

- Intelligent animals receive a scarcity of training signals, but may compensate via self-supervision by making and testing predictions about latent environment features
- The hippocampus is well suited to be a neural prerequisite for this process, as its evolution precedes the advent of “deep” forms of learning in the neocortex
- Moreover, the hippocampus is a nexus of multiple brain networks, and its representational contents are often predictive in nature for both sensory and higher order processes
- The hippocampus can maintain parallel representations on multiple timescales, meaning predictions can be verified independently in the near or distant future
- This perspective reconciles contemporary concepts in neuroscience and AI, with potential to understand key neural computations that may set basis of bio-inspired AI

Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) implemented using neural networks (ANNs) has achieved huge success by modeling intelligent behaviour as a feedforward input-output or stimulus-response mapping process. This is in part driven by modeling cognitive processes more generally as hierarchical processing streams similar to those found in the brain, in particular the sensory systems [1–4]. These AI systems, however, require millions of labeled training samples while the brain is able to learn with relatively little external supervision. Recent and future directions in AI have now begun to focus on modeling cognition in latent or embedded spaces and using methods involving the reuse of information over time. Here, we argue that the hippocampus, a phylogenetically old cortical structure with unique neural properties and a key involvement in memory formation and retrieval, is ideally suited for making and maintaining predictions about the future. As we argue, it does so via data-efficient learning processes which may computationally resemble prediction within lower dimensional latent spaces. We first overview how learning and memory are implemented in ANNs and the brain. Next, we discuss the evolutionary context and architecture of the hippocampus, which arose at the outset of “deep” learning in the brain. We then argue that representational contents in the hippocampus are predictive in content, and supported by a specialized microcircuitry that approximates long-term memory that is required for efficient predictive learning. Finally, we provide a theoretical basis for how unique properties of the hippocampus can improve the quality and quantity of “learnable” training experiences via latent space prediction. Though the hippocampus is present in all mammals, we argue it facilitates domain-general learning, including uniquely human abilities like advanced language, manual dexterity, and long term planning. Altogether this provides many exciting directions for AI research across many domains and helps to propagate proven computational solutions from AI back into human cognitive neuroscience.

Background

Learning and memory in ANNs and the brain

In modern ANNs, learning is the process of updating parameters, *i.e.*, weights of connections between neurons, based on a training signal. Training signals are typically derived from carefully curated, large datasets. Efficient algorithms, such as backpropagation of error [5], are able to determine which weight changes best optimize this mapping. Since learning is iterative, recent training iterations are favoured and can interfere with previous mappings. This is circumvented by employing a low learning rate and repeated, randomly ordered iterations through the dataset. These mappings are then held constant, evaluated, and then deployed for solving problems without further training, or sometimes with later “fine-tuning” by the same process when additional input and output data are made available.

Memory in ANNs is more complex than learning, and has many possible implementations. A good example is memory-augmented ANNs (MANNs) which are able to store 1:1 hard copies of information into external memory slots, which can be read later without interference from intervening timepoints [6–8]. In this way, forward time-translational equivariance is achieved - that is, a memory has the same fidelity whether it is recalled immediately or in the distant future (referred to hereafter as **time-equivariance**). Other systems, like the long- short-term memory network [9], are also popular. Yet, their memory decays within a small

number of iterations due to an issue known as the vanishing or exploding gradient problem [10]. Thus, for comparisons here, we will consider mainly MANNs as analogues for hippocampal memory.

In the brain, learning can be operationalized similarly: as a change in synaptic weights between neurons. The changes associated with a specific learning event (or iteration) are generally called its “engram” [11,12]. Memory as implemented in a MANN, however, is implausible in the brain because neurons usually undergo slow, gradual synaptic weight changes. That is, while it's possible to take an instantaneous “snapshot” in a MANN, in a brain such an operation would require strong one-shot synaptic changes to the relevant neurons. Widespread one-shot synaptic changes would likely cause interference with other mappings which ought to (for adaptability) remain relatively stable. However, there is one structure in the brain that, above all others, is able to approximate this “snapshotting” or time-equivariance: the hippocampus [13–15], a cortical region with a unique, interlocked anatomy in the mesial temporal lobe that indeed distantly resembles a seahorse when looked at it from superior. Within the hippocampus, representations pass through a highly unique structure called the dentate gyrus (DG) where engrams resist interference and are long-lasting [16,17], but are made in one-shot learning or real-time, perhaps due to phases of extreme neuron plasticity [18–20]. This could be considered a biological approximation of time-equivariance as in a MANN, and intuitively this matches our notion that episodic memory works similarly to a video capture that can be played back later. Behavioural and cognitive studies also show that the hippocampus is particularly important for making and maintaining episodic and spatial memories - that is, memories whose contents include a specific time and/or place [21–24]. Under complementary learning systems framework, this contrasts with neocortical forms of learning which are argued to take place over many time/place instances, being not tightly tied to any one learning experience, and are rather considered implicit, semantic, procedural, or habitual learning [25–27].

It is a simplification to suppose that memory takes place in the hippocampus while learning takes place in the neocortex. Fast and short-lasting synaptic changes and prolonged activity states (or representation maintenance) take place in other parts of the brain, supporting short-term memory [28–33]. These forms of memory both in ANNs and in the brain are necessary in tasks like change detection [34] or motion tracking [35–37], but their memory contents are continuously modified and short lasting [10]. Additionally, a MANN with a small memory capacity (or similarly, a temporally-masked Transformer - see Box 1) is more likely to engage recall after short delays compared to one with a large memory capacity, so this ANN architecture may also be an apt approximation of short-term neocortical memory. Conversely, within the hippocampus, synaptic changes can also be evoked gradually by repeated stimulation rather than in one-shot, suggesting that within this heterogeneous structure there is also gradual modification of information over protracted timespans, and therefore it is not purely a time-equivariant system. The view that the hippocampus acts as a MANN while the neocortex as a conventional feed-forward ANN, is a simplification that we will nevertheless employ for brevity.

Box 1: Transformers vs. MANNs

At present, Transformers [38,39] are considered the state-of-the-art ANN architecture, being used in many popular applications like large language models including ChatGPT and others. Recent work reveals a close conceptual similarity with MANNs [40]. Two unique features of Transformers are their optimization via self-supervised learning techniques and their use of self-attention [38,39,41]. Self-attention was originally conceived to reduce the search space of learning problems, as in time- or space- equivariance, by selecting only a subset of features from an input for further

processing [42]. For time series data, this could happen as follows: the full timeseries of an input are presented, and the processing of each timepoint is performed with the added context from one or several other “attended” timepoints. Similarly, if we were to write each timestep into one MANN memory slot, then the processing of the N th element can be interpreted with the L th and M th elements recalled as context. In some Transformers, the element N can be used to cue attention of items occurring both earlier or later, while in other cases temporal “masking” is applied such that cues are limited to attending only elements that occurred earlier, matching the constraints of real-time experience. The computation for “attending” uses a similarity metric between the N th element and all others, and [40] recently showed that under some circumstances, this computation is identical to other MANN networks like the Tolmann-Eichenbaum Machine (TEM) [43,44]. In summary, under some circumstances a Transformer is a form of short-term MANN (when the Transformer employs temporal masking) and under some implementations, a MANN is a form of Transformer (when all inputs are saved and the MANN uses read operations consisting of a similarity metric).

Latent-space predictive coding

Vast experience-dependent learning takes place within one animal or, especially, one human lifespan [45]. Evolution may shape the recognition of certain unconditioned stimuli that are intrinsic rewards or punishments, analogous to those provided under typical AI reinforcement learning paradigms like foraging tasks, game scores, or human-generated ratings. However, even the most prolific animals are unlikely to receive many external unconditioned stimuli within, for example, a day, but are nevertheless able to quickly acquire or fine-tune large experience-dependent behavioural repertoires. This contrasts conventional ANN paradigms, which typically require thousands-to-millions of training samples to learn even highly constrained tasks.

Self-supervised learning does not require labeled (or unconditioned) training data, but rather derives training signals from the environment itself. For example, this could include training by testing predictions about how some action will cause changes in a visual field - teaching the network about its action space and about the statistics or intuitive physics of its environment. This more closely replicates the real-world conditions of animal learning since they have a scarcity of labeled training data but engage in extensive self- and world exploration. Such predictive architectures are similar in concept to the predictive coding framework in neurosciences [46,47]. A recent overview [48] provides several critical stipulations for a predictive architecture based on ANN design requirements:

- Predictions should be made about latent space or low-dimensional “embedded” data rather than directly about high-dimensional future sensory data (Figure 1A). Latent spaces have many possible instantiations and therefore a non-negligible chance of coming true. For example: if I am feeding pigeons at a park and loudly clap my hands, I make the latent prediction that the pigeons will spook and fly away. I don’t make predictions about all features, like which direction each pigeon will fly, which will determine my experience at the retinal level and which is unlikely to match the actual environment. However, no matter which way the pigeons fly, they are likely to generate latent features like fluttering sounds and extended wings, which match the unfolding of my latent prediction.
- Additional optimizations beyond prediction are required. If my visual stream were trained solely to optimize its own predictions in the future, an optimal outcome could be achieved by making the same prediction regardless of the input, an issue also termed “representational collapse” (for example, see discussion by [45]). For example, a visual system could be trained to predict and map every visual field to the same latent-space representation, for example one we may call “blue circles”. Then, when I clap my hands and the pigeons fly away I will predict and subsequently see blue circles, cementing

my incorrect belief. [48] propose a secondary optimizer maximizing information content to ensure latent spaces also have discriminatory power.

- Predictions should be limited. In theory, optimal behaviour (or “solved” games) can be computed from all possible predictions $\text{Pred}(t_0, k)$ made at timepoint t_0 and k possible choices, resulting in a Markov chain of width k in cases where predictions are discretized (*e.g.*, as in chess) or an infinite space where they are not (as in the real world). In reverse, at the time of observation t_{0+N} after delay N , predictions from any past timepoint could be evaluated. However, in practice, both ANNs and animals have a limited capacity to make, store, and query predictions in a time-efficient manner.

The latter two points are less critical to the arguments forwarded here but nevertheless warrant consideration in future work given their solid theoretical backing. We will refer to the above framework as latent-space predictive coding (LSPC).

Figure 1. Analogies between the model proposed by LeCun (2022) [48] and brain components (only the visual modality is shown for simplicity). **A)** overview of LSPC [48]. Inputs (x) are fed through an encoder (Enc) to generate latent-space representations (s_x) while a prediction engine (Pred) given memory (z) estimates future latent-space representations (\tilde{s}_y). A contrast (D) between \tilde{s}_y and actual future (x_{t+N}) latent-space (s_y) determines the network training signal. The encoder’s information content ($R(s_x)$) is maximized to avoid representational collapse, while the predictor’s memory contents are compressed ($R(z)$) to reduce storage and search space. **B)** Analogous human brain regions, notably, with the hippocampus acting as the predictor. Only the ventral visual stream (VVS) and hippocampus (Hipp) are shown for simplicity, though multiple sensory processing streams project to the hippocampus.

We argue that the prediction component of LSPC models, the green box in Figure 1A, is instantiated by the hippocampus. The following arguments and corresponding sections support this notion: 1) The hippocampus is evolutionarily situated at the outset of “deep” biological learning, 2) the observed connectivity and representational contents of the hippocampus are suggestive of this role, and 3) time-equivariant memory supported by unique hippocampal microcircuitry offers theoretical gains in the quality and quantity of training signals that make it advantageous in this role.

1. Hippocampus as an evolutionary precursor to predictive learning

The peripheral nervous system, spinal cord, subcortex, and cortex can each be thought of as supporting different orders of magnitude in behavioural complexity (see Figure 2). Peripheral, spinal, and subcortical connectivity is genetically and developmentally coded. It remains relatively fixed after reaching maturity, and is optimized on an evolutionary timescale (Figure 1A-C). The cortex, however, is highly interconnected and plastic, making it amenable to complex experience-dependent learning as in ANNs. Such extensive and flexible connectivity enables learning that is highly nonlinear and “deep” in the sense that sensory information is abstracted from low-level to high-level representations that are generalizable [49–52]. Cross-

disciplinary research has shown similarities in functioning and in representational structure between the neocortex and current ANN models. For example, representational similarities have been demonstrated between convolutional neural networks and the neocortical ventral visual stream [53–55]. Examples also exist in other cognitive systems, such as shared features between large language models and the human language processing system [56]. However, we argue that the neocortex would not have evolved to this extent without training signals generated by the archicortex, or hippocampus.

Figure 2. Organization of the nervous system and evolution of paleo-, archi-, and neocortex. **A)** Body segments are each innervated by pairs of spinal relays. **B)** Spinal relay systems are minimally interconnected and minimally plastic, making them unsuitable for deep learning. **C)** The subcortex offers integration across distant body segments, but with limited plasticity. **D)** The cortex is highly interconnected and highly plastic, with some brain regions (including hippocampus) receiving transmodal sensory inputs making them suitable for LSPC. **E)** Human archicortex is maintained while neocortex is expanded. Data-driven dimensionality reduction of fMRI signals during naturalistic movie watching shows neocortical specialization towards somatomotor, visual, and auditory networks. Candidate regions for supporting LSPC should show convergence of modalities (*i.e.* a combination of all three networks, as in prefrontal, posterior parietal, and medial-temporal areas). Flatmapped cortex adapted from [57], gradient data from [58].

The evolution of the cortex can be simplified as occurring in three epochs: the paleocortex (consisting of our primary olfactory cortex), the archicortex (consisting of our hippocampi), and the neocortex (consisting of the bulk of our primary and association cortex; see Figure 2D-E). The paleocortex is amenable to complex learning, but is also a primary sensory region making it unsuitable for LSPC. It may be that training signals for this region were initially from unconditioned rewards (*e.g.*, dopaminergic rewards for behaviours like grooming, feeding, mating, and resting). The archicortex, or hippocampus, was next to evolve and is not tied directly to any one sensory modality, meaning that it receives latent inputs that have already been

processed by primary sensory cortices. This makes it the earliest cortical and latent region, and an attractive candidate region for prediction in LSPC, which can then inform increasingly latent processing during the expansion of the neocortex.

While we argue that the hippocampus arose to make predictions that provide training for primary sensory cortices, it is also true that the predictor would not be tractable without the concurrent evolution of appropriate encoders [48]. Expansion seen in later and more cognitively complex mammals is largely in the neocortex, which in humans is particularly extended in the frontal, parietal and temporal regions compared to other species [59]. This enlargement and repetitive structure (*i.e.*, canonical 6-layered columns [60–62]) suggests that the neocortex is scalable analogously to conventional ANNs: the addition of more units can increase performance and change representational contents without changes to the algorithmic processes of individual units. This is supported by cross-species studies: despite divergence in brain organization, different species are tethered by common processing in primary sensory and hippocampal areas but not high-order sensory and default mode cortical areas [63–65]. Thus there may have been an interplay whereby LSPC computations in the hippocampus remained relatively fixed while its input embedded representations from the neocortex became increasingly specialized. Thus, these two systems should be considered highly interdependent, and their early evolution likely goes hand-in-hand.

2. Hippocampal contents and computations

2.1. Hippocampal representational contents are predictive

Many neuroscientists think of the hippocampus as supporting spatial or episodic memory and not necessarily making predictions *per se*, but the notion that hippocampal memory traces contain not only veridical past information but also predictions about the future has broad support in the literature. Some particularly compelling examples from the human literature include “episodic future thinking” [66,67], hippocampal interactions with limbic and default mode brain networks during rest or imagining [44,68], and “boundary extension tasks” [69,70]. The rodent literature has tended to focus more on spatial processing in the hippocampus, asserting that it supports a “cognitive map” [13]. The cognitive map model is supported in part by the discovery of “place-” and “grid-” cells which activate when an animal visits a specific place or regular grid of places, respectively, in a known environment [13]. “Time-” cells have also been found that follow the same principle [71], as well as evidence for mapping of conceptual spaces in the human hippocampus [72]. For this reason and others, some research thus argues that the cognitive map provides a “predictive” map rather than a purely spatial one [73]. That is, a cognitive map in the hippocampus may act as a simulation engine supporting goal-directed navigation, but the same principle may apply to non-spatial domains as well, like navigating towards a social state. It has thus been argued that in early mammals, the hippocampus was used predominantly for 2D spatial navigation but as more domains of cognition, or latent spaces, arose with concurrent neocortical expansion, different types of information became represented in the hippocampus [63,74,75]. This helps bridge the literature on human and animal hippocampal functions: in addition to being foundational to our learning of space and time, the hippocampus may support predictions and, therefore, training signals about many other domains of cognition.

In humans, hippocampal connectivity is embedded within multiple macroscale functional networks, contributing to specific hippocampal computations and its role as a nexus connecting paralimbic, sensory,

and heteromodal association systems, such as the default mode network [63,67,76–81]. A broad involvement in multiple macroscale networks is compatible with the key role the hippocampus plays in numerous cognitive and affective processes, including memory and language function, together with affective reactivity, stress as well as spatial navigation [44,73,82–84]. This suggests that the hippocampus receives not only multimodal inputs, but also multiple levels of abstraction as they emerged through evolutionary time. Indeed, subjective episodic memory reports include not only sensory contents but also social, emotional, and goal-orienting information, sometimes including even precise imagery, language, narrative, and rhythms [21,85,86].

2.2. Hippocampal microcircuits and computation

Despite changes to its input regions, the microcircuitry of the hippocampus remains relatively conserved over evolutionary time and has been well characterized in humans and animals. In recent work [87], we proposed a simple organization that encapsulates many observed differences in hippocampal computation and representational contents along two perpendicular axes: subfield-related and anterior-posterior (Figure 3). Computation in the brain is thought to be driven by local or microcircuit connectivity, characterized by features like laminae, neuron morphology, arborization, synapse density, and receptor types at the microscale. Conversely, functional MRI reveals macroscopic organization and has shown differentiation in functional connectivity and task-evoked responses across the anterior-posterior axis of the hippocampus [88,89]. Specifically, the posterior hippocampus is connected to neocortical regions with more sensory specialization, including regions important for spatial processing and sensory detail, whereas the anterior hippocampus is connected to neocortical regions more involved in abstract thought. Since the microcircuitry and therefore computational specialization is nearly constant between anterior and posterior hippocampus [87], they are likely performing similar computations and it is rather their macroscale connectivity (or input contents) that differs. This mirrors the principle that representational content, or abstraction, differs between species while microstructure and computation are relatively conserved.

Figure 3. Computation and connectivity in the hippocampus. **A)** The human hippocampus has a complex folding structure that can be unfolded and simplified into two organizational axes: **B)** continuous anterior-posterior axis that differs in functional connectivity to the rest of the brain and **C)** discrete subfields that differ microstructurally (and computationally). **D)** Hippocampal connectivity places it at the apex of sensory streams which likely expanded over evolutionary time. Since anterior hippocampus contains more latent or abstract representations, it may be connected with higher neocortical regions, either remaining their primary training signal or simply accessing representations generated by additional training processes. **E)** Canonical hippocampal circuits are shown in

unfolded space, which can be seen in parallel units across an anterior-posterior axis but differentiated subfield architectures. DG = dentate gyrus, CA = cornu ammonis, Sub = subicular complex, aLEC = antero-lateral entorhinal cortex, pmEC = postero-medial entorhinal cortex. DG is omitted from surface meshes to avoid occlusion, and a gap is left in unfolded space to signify its topological discontinuity from the rest of the hippocampus.

The hippocampus is a highly heterogeneous structure with respect to microstructure, specifically between its subfields. Canonically, the hippocampus makes up a loop wherein signals flow from neighbouring entorhinal cortex (EC) to DG, through the CA fields and the subicular complex, and then back to adjacent EC. This “big loop” recurrence is suggestive of attractor dynamics wherein the network starts with a given input pattern and iteratively self-stimulates until it reaches a stable, previously engraved pattern or attractor state achieved through many repeated input exposures [90,91]. This is a possible mechanism supporting memory recall or pattern completion given a partial cue [80,92]. A dense collection of recurrent collaterals in CA3 (but also other subfields, see [87]) may also act as a nested attractors within this greater network, perhaps providing multiple scales of encoding and recall [93,94]. “Skip” or monosynaptic connections bypass the DG and some CA fields, which may provide a mechanism to relate incoming latent sensory data directly to settled attractor states for computing difference function or prediction error [95–97]. As noted in [87], these canonical circuits are a simplification of the actual spatial distribution of hippocampal microstructure, and ideally computations should be mapped to microstructural features directly rather than to canonical subfields [87]. Another way to consider the hippocampus is as a stepwise gradient that is more “neocortex-like” towards the subicular complex and rhinal cortices and more unique towards the CA fields (Figure 3, right). At the apex of the CA fields, the DG is most distinct, consisting of a separate layer of dense granule neurons [98–100]. The DG has a well documented role in pattern separation [16,101], but also is the primary site of human adult neurogenesis in the brain [102–104]. As new neurons integrate into the DG, they go through a phase of hyper excitability and plasticity [18,105], making them particularly well-suited for one-shot learning. Thus, while the hippocampus has many specialized microstructural features including multiple scales of local recurrence, the DG and its roles in pattern separation and one-shot learning are highly distinct from the neocortex and may support high-fidelity approximations of time-equivariance in the brain.

3. Advantages to hippocampal-supported predictive learning

3.1. Dense and frequent training signals

Learning via reinforcement or unconditioned training signals is not only infrequent in naturalistic settings, but it is also less informationally dense than predictive training. That is, reinforcement training typically only consists of a scalar, with positive values indicating good and negative values indicating bad outcomes. Episodic memory in the brain, conversely, has high representational capacity, meaning that many aspects of a memory can be compared to a present experience. Secondly, the hippocampus engages powerful pattern separation such that latent information encoded by the DG can persist for a relatively long time. This also means that at a given timepoint, there is a large memory bank that can be queried to lend context or make a predictive comparison against the current experience. Similarly, a given experience can be recalled in the future many times. These cases both increase the amount of possible learning samples from a fixed number of experiences. This is important for AI since it helps shift the rate-limiter from the availability of data to the availability of hardware, in this case the size of the memory bank. This shift is stronger than typical LSPC methods since memory items are reused, therefore shifting the burden of computation more towards

querying and selective maintenance of memory and less on active exploration of the environment (whether real or simulated). In terms of animal learning, this means that in theory, an animal with a hippocampus can learn more from less real-world experience.

3.2. Recall of predictions

If we suppose that a DG-supported memory or LSPC representation are highly pattern separated, then as a consequence it is unlikely that it will be recalled, even where appropriate. In this case, other hippocampal subfields including CA3 or “big loop” recurrences may perform pattern completion to approximate an attractor state, which then achieves the similarity threshold for DG reactivation allowing for further precision within that attractor subspace. That is, in a sense, the DG may augment the capacity or precision of a broader hippocampal attractor network [106].

Extant models of the hippocampus tend to focus on its pattern completion supported by its high internal recurrence, particularly in subfield CA3 [80,92]. There are many ANN systems that achieve pattern completion via attractor dynamics, but as an example we will consider restricted Boltzmann machines (RBM) [107]. The process of training a RBM uses a biologically-plausible Hebbian learning rule (*i.e.*, neurons that fire together wire together - increasing synapse strengths or model weights proportionately to their activity level). With a high learning rate or with multiple training iterations, some neurons will become bound and can reactivate one another in response to even a partial input or cue. RBMs were inspired by the brain and some have argued that the neocortex can be thought of as a very large RBM training over long time spans (or in other words, with many stimuli and a slow learning rate) [108]. So why have a hippocampus at all? Or in other words, is the hippocampus simply a vestigial version of the neocortex? Complementary (or dual-process) learning systems models of hippocampal function suggest that while both the neocortex and hippocampus are continuously learning, the latter does so at a higher rate and with the support of unique properties like interference-resistant DG representations [25]. Other recent work suggests that some subsystems in the hippocampus or extended hippocampal network may show an intermediate learning rate making a contiguous span of timescales for learning [94]. It may be that the neocortex has such a slow learning rate that millions of training samples are required to consolidate a stable representation [109]. The hippocampus, on the other hand, may have a tradeoff wherein learning rate is high, but large memory capacity or pattern separation is required to avoid interference.

3.3. Non-locality of engrams

Occasionally, the same activity signatures of an experience become reactivated across large swathes of the neocortex much later than the original experience. This is generally referred to as reinstatement, and is orchestrated by the hippocampus [26,109–111]. Though the mechanisms of this reinstatement are not fully understood, it is clear that it relies largely on indirect connections that likely follow a top-down or reverse sensory hierarchy, since the hippocampus is not directly connected to primary sensory areas [112]. Thus, reinstatement does not obey locality constraints, a common criticism on the biological plausibility of popular deep learning algorithms like backpropagation of error [5,113–116]. It may be the case that reinstatement also occurs simultaneously with bottom-up sensory experiences, making contrasts between the present and predicted representations possible at multiple levels in the sensory hierarchy. That is, top-down and bottom-up signaling could be considered error and activity representations that are necessary to compute the training gradients or local updates in ANNs. This is challenging to test in the brain, however:

it is methodologically difficult to rigorously detect offline reinstatement even without concurrent bottom-up activity (see [110]).

Conclusions and future directions

In conclusion, we argue that hippocampal learning was a critical step towards animal intelligence, and analogues in ANN design are critical to AGI. We overview evidence that the hippocampus 1) closely predates “deep” learning in evolution, 2) maintains latent predictions, and 3) offers unique features like the ability to maintain engrams over arbitrary time delays (time equivariance). These features can theoretically greatly augment neocortical learning through a process like latent space predictive coding (LSPC). We believe this helps to bridge the explanatory gap between ANN learning which requires extensive supervision even for highly constrained tasks, and animal learning which is data-efficient, naturalistic, and largely self-driven.

It is important to note that the hippocampus is likely not the only source of neocortical training signals. For example, patients and animals with hippocampal damage do show relatively intact learning on some tasks. For example, reward-driven learning [117–119] and fear conditioning [120,121] are possible even after hippocampal lesions. Additionally, some patients with hippocampal damage show spared learning in other domains involving gradual or repeated exposure learning [122–124]. Thus, it may be that the hippocampus plays an elective but facilitative role in domain-general learning wherein learning can proceed in its absence but requires more and denser training samples than usual [125–127]. All this is consistent with the notion that the hippocampus provides powerful training signals for the rest of the brain, but additional parallel optimization processes are likely at play. Indeed, it was also noted in [48] that additional optimizers must necessarily be present in an ANN beyond LSPC in order to avoid the issue of representational collapse.

Many open questions remain in our understanding of unsupervised natural and artificial learning. Firstly, what is the optimal tradeoff between memory capacity and query time? While this is likely dependent on the environment and goals, human and animal performance may provide insight when trying to replicate certain behaviours or systems that have already been optimized to evolutionary niches. For example, this could inform whether MANNs should employ a similarity metric for querying memories, or an additional ANN acting as an operator, or other heuristics like least- or most-recently used location indexing [7,8]. Relatedly, though the models of hippocampal subdivisions and function presented here are simplistic, many complexities exist within hippocampal microcircuitry and in its interactions with the rest of the brain. In particular, its offline interplay with the default mode neocortical network could support systems for memory modification, elaboration towards prediction, heuristics for recall, consolidation to the neocortex, or other operations latent spaces. Secondly, when a prediction error occurs, should one update the current sensory model, the memory, both, or neither? In other words, should the sensory hierarchy be tuned to align with past experiences, or should the memories be updated with new information? Perhaps a memory is judged by another system as inappropriate, and so neither should be updated. Biology rarely employs pure computational processes [128], and thus updates to both probably always occur in degrees. Thirdly, recent work suggests uniquely human adaptations in the hippocampus that may help support learning in uniquely human domains, like highly prosocial behaviour, advanced planning, and language [86]. Thus a better understanding of interspecies differences in hippocampal structure may inform advances in these task domains. Finally, while training ANNs in increasingly naturalistic arenas, we should be wary of the ethical

consequences. In particular, training in naturalistic tasks leads to representational contents that are more reflective of the natural world. In addition, some neuroscientists have proposed that memory is a critical component to the subjective phenomenology of consciousness [129]. Thus systems developed in the ways described here could have subjective phenomenology of the same world we inhabit, or aspects of it, creating the potential for conflict but also for new perspectives.

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